

LASER INDUCED FREESTANDING GRAPHENE PAPERS FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A new route for producing freestanding graphene papers (GPs) with simple and scalable process was proposed based on the novel strategy of laser induced graphene (LIG) by introducing polyimide paper (PI paper) as the precursor medium. With the optimized protocol, the size of laser induced graphene paper (LIGP) is up to 40×35 cm². Additionally, structure-property relationship has been systematically studied to advice people the preparation of LIGP with tunable mechanical, electrical, piezoresistive, and joule-heating, characteristics, which are advantageous for assembling multifunctional composite structures, e.g. flame retardant, de-icing, and self-sensing. Considering swiftness, cost-effectiveness and scalability along with flexible, shape-customizable, and integratable natures, we highly expect the escalation of LIGP for commercialization, roll-to-roll manufacturing, and novel assembly of next-generation composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymeric composites (FRPs) are extremely important as unique structural materials for a wide applications in different fields such as commercial & battle aircrafts, boats & submarines, and oil transmission pipelines etc. In the past decade, substantial attention has been paid for the research and development of next generation of FRPs with built-in multi-functionality for realizing non-flammable, self-sensing, identifying, and de-icing. Different approaches and doped materials were attempted to the preparation of smart FRPs and impart them specific functions.

Carbon materials were most used as multifunctional fillers for the construction of multifunctional composites. The current fabrications of functional composites are serious rely on the solution phase assembly, in which a key step is transforming mixtures of carbon materials and polymer composites to homogenous solution [1-3]. Many literatures on traditional methods pay particular attention to carbon black [4] and carbon nanotubes [5,6], both them have high conductivity and excellent mechanical strength. In addition, these two materials have a good dispersion in various polymer solutions. But only few studies focused on multifunctional composites based on graphene or graphene doped multifunctional composites. All the traditional methods are limited in practical and industrial applications, owing to difficult dispersion of raw materials [7], time-consuming processes [8], high energy consumption or expensive fabrication costs [9-10]. Considering the complexity of traditional production process and the increasing demands, it is necessary to find a new effective way to prepare multi-functional composites.

LIG has been proposed as a novel, environmental-friendly, cost effective and efficient strategy for graphene formation [11]. Besides, the tunable morphologies, properties, and functionalities of LIG for different application purposes can be easily obtained by modifying laser conditions [12]. In our previous study [13], benefiting from the unique spatial fiber network arrangements and free spaces of polyimide paper, we first proposed the fabrication of LIGP using polyimide paper as carbon precursors. By virtue of excellent mechanical flexibility, high electrical conductivity and low gas permeability, LIGP shows high response sensitivity as sensors and long ignition time as non-flammable layer.

In the present work, multi-functional LIGP embedded smart FRPs were successfully prepared. This smart composite has various functions including flame retardant, de-icing, *in-situ* curing monitoring, structural health monitoring and liquid sensing monitoring. During the combustion tests, the ignition time of LIGP is 107s, more than five times that of pure FRP (18s). Through the change of resistance of

embedded LIGP, we have achieved monitoring of the curing process and structural health monitoring of composites. Besides, the smart composite also could remove a large ice beg on its surface within 5 minutes. At last, LIGP was used for the construction of liquid sensor array, this array was successfully layout for mapping the distribution of different fluid emissions on composite structures. Related mechanisms to the mentioned functions was proposed. We highly anticipate the escalation of LIGP for commercialization, roll to roll manufacturing, and multimodal composites safety-assurance applications.

Figure 1 (a, b) Photographs of the largest LIGP and the schematic diagram of roll-to-roll manufacturing; (c) is the photograph of LIGP liquid sensor, (d) SEM images of LIGP processed by 1.125W laser at a low (scale = 100 μm) magnification, (e) TEM images of LIGP-1.125 under low (scale = 100 nm) and high magnification (inset, scale = 5 nm), and (f) Raman and XRD spectra of LIGP processed by 1.125 W.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 LIGP Fabrication. Polyimide (PI) paper (Cat.# Yilun-P-90) was purchased from PolyKing, Changchun. Laser irradiation system (DLS 2.3, Universal Laser Systems, Inc.) equipped with a CO₂ laser with the wavelength of 10.6 μm was used for irradiating PI paper to generate graphene paper line by line. Both sides of commercial PI paper were wholly irradiated by the same laser power. With fixed line space (100 μm), image density (500 PPI) and scan rate (2 in. s⁻¹), varied laser powers (0.875–1.75 W) with increments of 0.125 W were used to scribe line-by-line on both sides of PI paper. All experiments were performed under ambient atmosphere.

2.2 Structural Characterization and Performance Evaluation. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed with JEOL JSM 7001F at 10 kV to examine microstructures of the graphene paper generated by CO₂ laser irradiation. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were taken using an 80 KeV JEM 2100F (JEOL Inc.) for evaluation of LIGP at nano scale. TEM samples were prepared by cutting small pieces of LIGP, followed by sonication for half an hour in ethyl alcohol and dropping the LIGP-alcohol suspension on the Cu grid. A Horiba HR800 Raman microscope using 532 nm excitation laser at the power of 5 mW was employed to obtain Raman spectra. Rigaku D/max 2550 with Cu Kα radiation ($\lambda = 1.54^\circ$) was used to obtain XRD pattern.

2.3 Preparation of LIGP Embedded Smart Composites. FRP was prepared as introduced in our previous work^[14]. 3×3 cm² LIGP was used for the combustion test. Firstly, the special adhesive was sprayed on the surface of FRP, LIGP was fixed on the surface of FRP until the adhesive dried. Then, both sides of LIGP-FRP composites were fixed by two clamps. Outer flame of the alcohol lamp as a fire source for the combustion tests. LIGP was sandwiched in FRP was used for de-icing, in-situ curing monitoring and structural health monitoring. The curing temperature is 120 °C. During the de-icing test, input power is 5.0W. All digital photos were taken by Canon EOS 5D Mark II.

2.4 Fabrication of LIGP Liquid Sensor Arrays on Composites. The sensors used for array construction were 1×1cm² with two 20 mm antennas as electrodes. All sensors were stuck to the surface of FRP by a special caking agent (UM super 77). Then, conductive silver paste (MSE2023MC, NanoMSE Corp.) was printed through a 0.56 mm syringe tip by the fluid dispensing system (Ultimus™ V, Nordson Corp.) equipped with a Nordson E3 stage. The dispensing pressure and moving speed were 60 psi and 50 mm/s, respectively. A few minutes later, linear electrodes on the surface of composites successfully connected two antennas of each sensor and formed an electrode matrix. Electrical isolation between every cross point of electrodes was pasted by epoxy gel. After sensor array construction and silver writing, an Iwata HP-CS airbrush nozzle (with Iwata IS-50 air compressor) equipped on the E3 stage controller was applied and programmed to move sequentially and repeatedly for acetone coating. The switch control system (2260B Keithley) with Lab View program was applied to realize real-time monitoring and record of the resistance change of the sensor array.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Structural characterization of LIGP

Compared with traditional graphene paper preparation, LIGP displays more advantages. LIGPs are more feasible for large-area and continuous preparation. Figure 1a and 1b demonstrates the schematic of roll to roll LIGP fabrication and the largest size of LIGP (35×40cm²) prepared in our lab. Figure 1c is the 1×1cm² liquid sensing device used in later experiment. It is beneficial to design and utilize various shapes in different fields. High production efficiency also provides great possibilities for various composites applications. Additionally, the cost of LIGP fabrication is much less than other methods which need amounts of polymer/carbon nanotubes or graphene solutions and complicated steps. Accordingly, we highly expect to realize roll-to-roll continuous manufacturing for production of LIGP as soon as possible.

To characterize the laser-induced structure, SEM, TEM, Raman and X-ray diffraction were carried out. Figure 1d shows the surface and the cross section of LIGP sensor processed by 1.125 W laser (denoted as LIGP-1.125), where line-by-line LIG features and the whole LIG layers are clearly

presented. TEM characterization further confirmed the microstructure of LIG. Figure 1e reveals that wrinkled LIG contains amounts of disordered graphene fringes. The high resolution TEM image inset shows the few-layer LIG and characteristic d-spacing (0.34 nm). Raman spectra of LIG-1.125 in the top panel of Figure 1(f) displays characteristic peaks for graphene at $\sim 1343\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (D peak), $\sim 1583\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (G peak), and $\sim 2690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (2D peak). D peak originates from the vibration of sp^2 carbon bonds induced by defects of graphene. G peak is the stretching vibration of sp^2 atomic pair peak. 2D peak originates from second-order zone-boundary phonons. The I_G/I_D intensity ratio is 1.1, indicating high degree graphitization of LIG. The bottom panel of Figure 1(f) reveals the XRD pattern of LIG with two strong peaks centering respectively at $2\theta = 26.3$ and $2\theta = 43.5$. This further confirms the presence of the multilayered in-plane structure of graphene with the interlayer spacing of 0.34 nm, which is consistent with the results obtained by TEM.

Figure 2 SEM images of LIGP processed at different power from 0.875w to 1.75w, (a) sheets structure, (b) curled porous structure, (c) fiber structure, scale bar = 1 μm .

Laser power could control structures and morphologies of LIGP. We also proved that with the tuning of laser power, LIGP exhibits different types of hierarchical structures. Figure 2a to c reveal the dynamic evolution of microstructures under the function of laser power. At 0.875 W, thick network structures appear with amounts of nano-pores. At the enhanced power of 1.375 W, the network structures become thinner, forming a honeycomb-like structure and intertwine together to form a porous structure. With the stepwise increase of power to 1.75 W, the honeycomb-like and porous structure ruptures to graphene fibers. In the above process, a tremendous change is found in morphologies of LIGP that majority of the thin network and porous structures have randomly broken into oriented and entangled fibers. The precise control of LIGPs with varied structures is instructive for the mechanisms of fire-retardant and liquid sensing which mentioned in the next part.

3.2 LIGP was used for protecting composites from fire hazardous

Figure 3 Digital photos of the burning test of LIGP, the pristine and LIGP attached composites. Combustion test of pure FRP and LIGP-FRP (LIGP bonded on both sides).

Flame retardant property is very important for composites. As shown in Figure 3, LIGP exhibits excellent flame retardant property, the ignition time as long as 107s. The reasons are mainly attribute to the dense and continuous structure of graphene sheets, which can prevent oxygen from entering inner structure of material. Additionally, based on the high thermal conductivity of graphene, heat can be quickly transferred and dispersed to other locations, and preventing the fire from spreading. LIGP has great potential in flame retardant fields.

LIGP was used for flame retardant layer of FRP. LIGP was attached on the surface of FRP by special adhesive. As Figure 3 shows, ignition time of pure FRP is 18s, while the ignition time of LIGP-FRP is 56s. Compared to pure FRP, the ignition time of LIGP-FRP is third that of pure FRP. The above mentioned results confirmed excellent flame retardant property of LIGP, it has great potential as a novel fire retardant shield for reducing FRPs from fire hazards in the future.

To better understand the flame retardant mechanism, we proposed the correlation between porous structure and gas permeability. Combustion mechanism of polymers is that the increasing temperature results in polymer bond scission, and then the volatile fraction of the resulting polymer fragments diffuses into the air and creates a combustible gaseous mixture [15,16]. At last, when the concentration of gaseous mixture ignites reaches the critical point with the temperature reaches the auto-ignition. As we know, gas permeability was decided by porosity and distribution of pore sizes. As Figure 2 shown, LIGP have numerous nano pores and big porosity. So, LIGP acting as a protective layer which limit the transfer of decomposition gases from the polymeric matrix underneath. The combustible gases can be physically separated from the oxygen, preventing the combustion process from being sustained. Interestingly, different from traditional flame retardant material which could be burned to ash, LIGP-FRP can maintain its original integrity even after long time burning.

3.3 LIGP for in-situ monitoring FRP curing and structural health monitoring

Benefiting from our previous study on in-situ monitoring FRP curing process, based on excellent conductivity of LIGP, Figure 4 shows a novel concept of monitoring of FRP with LIGP. The real-time resistance of LIGP embedded in the prepreg was monitored during the whole curing process.

Figure 4 Prepreg melt and curing process of hierarchical composites registered by the real-time resistance change of the embedded smart LIGP sensor. Melt stage: 150-288 sec (black curve); balance stage: 288-350 sec (red curve); curing stage: 350-2000 sec (blue curve).

By correlating the resistance changes with physical states in composite manufacturing, to better understand the monitoring mechanism of curing process, we divided the whole process into three specific stages (three inset images in Figure 4). The first is melt stage, from 150 to 288 sec, the resistance of LIGP has a sharply increase with the temperature increasing to 120°C, because the resin molecules continuously penetrate and wet the inner network structure of graphene and deposited on surface of the graphene sheets/fibers to result in expansion and even to isolate sheet/sheet or fiber/fiber

contacts, which causes the significant resistance increase. Furthermore, the curing process enters a balance stage, the constant value of dR/R_0 from 288 to 350 sec was observed. It can be explained that the resin molecules undergo a short flow balance stage assisted. Continuing with the curing process, the high levels of cross-linking density of resin molecules would cause a drastic increase of the system viscosity and volumetric shrink-age of the system. The sharply decrease of dR/R_0 from ~ 398 to ~ 2 also was observed when the processing time ranges from 350 to 7000 sec. The obvious decrement of dR/R_0 are mainly induced by physical/chemical changes in the cross-linking reaction and the concomitant variations of system viscosity, as well as the development of matrix shrinkage caused by phase transformation of gelation. At last, the LIGP network with infiltrated resin shrinks accordingly to cause its conductive paths closing together to have higher packing density [17].

Figure 5 Smart FRP composites with the integration of LIGP for deformations/failures detecting

After molding, the embedded LIGP sensor is also used for diagnosing deformations and failures of the FRP. Figure 5 shows the detail results, based on the varied piezo-resistive performance at different stages of the tension-to-failure process, LIGP sensor could accurately predict the level of elastic deformation ($GF=0.5$), initiation and development of micro-cracks ($0.5 < GF < 29.1$) and catastrophic damage ($GF=\infty$). The related mechanisms are attributed to the changing contact resistance of graphene sheets or fibers. Under normal conditions, graphene sheets/fibers contact with each other closely, when the smart FRP has a certain deformation under external force, it will drive the inner structure of graphene sheets/fibers separation, and resulting in bigger contact resistance.

3.4 LIGP for de-icing

Figure 6 LIGP embedded FRP composites for de-icing

Interestingly, inspired by Joule-heating property, LIGP sandwiched in a FRP laminate was successfully used for de-icing. As Figure 6 shows, with the input power of 5.0 W, the surface temperature of FRP reaches to 215 °C in 30 sec, the heated temperature is able to completely melt a large piece of ice that stayed on the surface of FRP in a -20 °C freezer within 5 min. Compared to

traditional mechanical de-icing methods, LIGP embedded FRP could removing ice more quickly and gently without damage for composites.

3.5 LIGP sensor array was used for protecting composites from harmful liquids

LIGP was not only used for non-flammable layer, structure health monitoring and de-icing, but also protect composites from corrosion liquids. Based on our previous study, LIGP display high sensitivity to organic solvents [13]. Attributed to the simple fabrication and controllable sensitivity, LIGP liquid sensor with customized shape and optimized performance is highly promising for protecting composites from corrosive organic solvents. Figure 7a and 7b shows the schematic of large-area deployment on surface of composites by applying a 5×5 sensors array for liquid sensing. By spray coating acetone and monitoring the relative resistance change of sensor array assisted by a switch control system, each sensor element shows different response sensitivity because they were covered by different amounts of acetone. Figure 7c shows the sensitivity of the sensors in the third column during the acetone coating process. It is obvious that sensors closed to the nozzle contact more acetone and exhibit higher sensitivity. The sensor array can predict the location where the composite is exposed to acetone and the degree of erosion by organic solvents. As shown in the 3D bar plot, the dR/R_0 distribution of all 25 sensors accurately restores the spraying process. With the enlarged spraying area by elevating the nozzle, 6 sensors in the middle of array exhibit relatively higher sensitivity (the average of $dR/R_0=1.3\%$) than sensors in other locations (the average of $dR/R_0=0.12\%$). We also proposed the possible sensing mechanism of LIGP. At the initial stage, when the acetone enters the internal structure of LIGP, a new cascaded graphene-acetone molecule-graphene hybrid structure come into being together with the generation of capillary forces. Then, as charge carriers must pass through the solvent molecules, the hybrid structure barricade charge carriers, which leads to lower carrier mobility. During the infiltration process, the network structure of graphene swells slightly, and at the same time the increments of distance between two adjacent graphene pores and fibers prolong the migration distance of charge carriers. The two factors commonly result in the great decrease in the conductivity of LIGP and the increase in the contact resistance of the internal structure. Additionally, it is highly anticipated that the LIGP liquid sensor array can protect composites from organic solvents and acid rain, it also can predict and monitor the degree of erosion of composites by harmful liquids.

Figure 7 (a) Schematic diagram of fabrication of LIGP liquid sensor array on composites, (b) LIGP liquid sensors and arrays adhesion on surface of composites by silver electrodes, (c) Real-time resistance changes of LIGP liquid sensor at different location during spray-coating acetone (from left to right are the schematic of spray coating process and sensitivity of the whole sensor array, respectively).

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, a novel LIGP was used for multifunctional FRPs construction. We achieved the integration of flame retardant, de-icing, *in-situ* curing monitoring, structural health monitoring and liquid sensing monitoring. Flame retardant time of LIGP attached composites was three times that of pure composites. The embedded LIGP sensor in composites was used for predicting the resin curing process and the deformations/failures of the molded composites. It also could remove a large ice beg on its surface quickly based on the excellent joule-heating property. Additionally, based on the higher conductivity and nonpolar surface, LIGP exhibit fast response liquid sensing behavior. 5×5 LIGP sensor array was successful designed and assembled for monitoring and predicting the locations of composites where threatened by harmful liquids. LIGP was demonstrated in this work can be highly valuable in multi-functional smart composites preparation. Various mechanisms based on the mentioned functions were proposed. At last, we highly anticipate the commercialization of LIGP for multi-functional smart FRPs construction.

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